

Diagnostic and Therapeutic Challenges in Unicystic Ameloblastoma: A Case-Based Review

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Abstract

Unicystic ameloblastoma is a benign, locally aggressive odontogenic tumor that typically presents as a well-defined radiolucent lesion. It most commonly affects the mandible, especially in the molar-ramus region. This case report presents a 55-year-old male who presented with pain and swelling in the lower left posterior region of the jaw. Clinical examination revealed a localized swelling, and radiographic imaging showed a multilocular radiolucent lesion involving the left body of the mandible. An incisional biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of unicystic ameloblastoma, with histopathological features including odontogenic epithelium lining the cystic lumen, islands of epithelial proliferation, and a fibrocellular capsule. The patient was advised to undergo surgical enucleation of the cyst; however, the patient did not follow through with the procedure. This case highlights the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate management to prevent recurrence and further complications of unicystic ameloblastoma.

Introduction

Ameloblastomas, the most common benign odontogenic tumour, account for 10% of all odontogenic tumours and 1% of jaw tumours and cysts.¹ It is a locally aggressive, slow-growing, and persistent tumour that may start in the tooth-forming epithelium, including the enamel organ, odontogenic rests of Malassez, reduced enamel epithelium, and odontogenic cyst lining.² Ameloblastomas can develop peripherally or centrally inside the bone, without an intraosseous component in the soft tissues covering the alveolar ridge. Intraosseous lesions are of two types solid/conventional/multicystic and unicystic³. The ameloblastoma is most commonly seen in the posterior mandible, but may also arise in the maxilla and anterior aspect of the jaws. The radiographic appearance ranges from a unilocular to a multilocular radiolucency⁴. Ameloblastomas are rare in children, with most cases occurring in patients between 20 and 50 years of age. A unicystic variant of the ameloblastoma tends to occur during teenage years and has been reported to exhibit a less aggressive behavior⁵.

Unicystic ameloblastoma (UA), a variant of ameloblastoma first described by Robinson and Martinez in 1977, refers to those cystic lesions that show clinical and radiologic

characteristics of an odontogenic cyst but in histologic examination show a typical ameloblastomatous epithelium lining part of the cyst cavity with or without luminal and/or mural tumor proliferation. The tumor arises either as a de novo lesion or it develops due to neoplastic transformation of the preexisting cystic epithelium. Young people are mostly affected. Unicystic ameloblastoma produces painless swelling of the jaw with expansion of the cortical plates and disturbance in occlusion, etc. Some lesions can be asymptomatic. The lesion often exhibits a well-circumscribed, large unilocular, radiolucent area in the bone that often surrounds the crown of an impacted 3rd molar tooth⁶

Case Report

A 55-year-old male reported to the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology with a chief complaint of pain and swelling in the lower left posterior region of the jaw for the past 15 days. The pain was gradual in onset, intermittent in nature, and throbbing in type. It was associated with swelling on the same side, which was initially small in size and gradually increased to its present dimensions. On extraoral examination, a single, localized swelling was observed on the left side of the face, approximately 2.5 × 2.5 cm in size. It extended anteroposteriorly from the corner of the mouth to about 2–3 cm short of the angle of the mandible. Superoinferiorly, it extended from approximately 2 cm below a line drawn from the corner of the mouth to the tragus of the ear, down to the lower border of the mandible. The swelling was roughly oval in shape, with the overlying skin appearing normal in color. The surface was smooth, and the borders were well-defined (Figure 1). On intraoral examination, vestibular obliteration was noted in relation to teeth 35, 36, and 37. Paraesthesia was present on the lower labial mucosa on the left side.

Based on the patient's history and clinical examination, a provisional diagnosis of ameloblastoma involving the left body of the mandible was made. The differential diagnoses considered were calcifying epithelial odontogenic tumor, odontogenic keratocyst, and dentigerous cyst. Orthopantomogram (OPG) and cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) were performed. The OPG revealed a well-defined, multilocular, completely radiolucent lesion located in the left parasymphysis and body of the mandible, extending from the mesial aspect of tooth 33 to the distal aspect of tooth 37. A corticated border was observed from tooth 33 to the mesial of tooth 36, while a non-corticated border was noted from the distal of

tooth 36 to the distal of tooth 37. Loss of lamina dura was evident with teeth 35, 36, and 37, and root resorption was observed in relation to tooth 36. The lesion also showed involvement of the superior border of the inferior alveolar nerve canal (Figure 2). Axial sections of the CBCT revealed thinning and expansion of the buccal cortical plate and loss of the lingual cortical plate (Figure 3). Loss of the superior border of the inferior alveolar canal was also evident. In the longitudinal section, a scalloped border was noted (Figure 4).

An incisional biopsy was obtained from the lesion site (Figure 5). Hematoxylin and eosin-stained sections revealed a cystic lumen lined by odontogenic epithelium, 3–4 cell layers thick. The basal cells appeared tall and columnar, showing reversal of nuclear polarity, hyperchromatism, nuclear vacuolization, and subepithelial hyalinization. Proliferation of the epithelial lining into the lumen forming small islands was noted. The surrounding fibrocellular stroma contained numerous small islands and cords of odontogenic epithelium, along with collagen fibers, fibroblasts, and mild inflammatory infiltrate. These features were suggestive of unicystic ameloblastoma. The patient was advised to undergo surgical enucleation of the cyst; however, the patient did not report for the scheduled procedure.

Fig – 1-Oval swelling with distinct border

Fig-2: A well defined multilocular completely radiolucent lesion present in Left parasymphysis and body of mandible

Fig - 3: Thinning and expansion of buccal cortical plate and loss of lingual cortical plate

Fig - 4: Longitudinal section shows scalloped border.

Fig – 5: Incisional biopsy

Fig – 6: Luminal, Intraluminal, and Mural Variations :
features of unicystic ameloblastoma

Treatment

The treatment of unicystic ameloblastoma involves thorough curettage and enucleation⁴. The treatment varies in the case of recurrent unicystic ameloblastoma, where resection of the mandible is performed. The treatment of the luminal and intraluminal type of unicystic ameloblastoma remains to be enucleation and curettage whereas in the mural type of unicystic ameloblastoma, treatment plan depends on whether the fibrous wall of the cyst is infiltrated by typical follicular or plexiform pattern.

Discussion:-

This case report is a rare clinical behavior and radiographic appearance of unicystic ameloblastoma affecting the left parasymphysis and body of mandible, associated with mild jaw pain, swelling and numbness as main clinical symptoms.

Ameloblastomas are slow-growing, persistent, locally invasive benign odontogenic tumours. Their capacity for fast growth can lead to abnormalities in the morphology of bones⁵. The first thorough description of ameloblastoma was published by Broca in 1868. At presentation, the age range is 4 to 92 years, with the median age being 35.9 years. The mandible accounts for 80% of cases, with the molars and ramus being the most common sites. The incidence is highest in the third and fourth decades of life⁵.

Unicystic ameloblastoma, which refers to cystic lesions that typically manifest in the second or third decade of life, is a less common variant of ameloblastoma⁶. 6%–15% of intraosseous ameloblastomas are caused by UA⁷. The lesion is basically a well-defined, frequently large monocystic cavity with a lining, focally but rarely entirely composed of odontogenic (ameloblastomatous) epithelium. The term unicystic is derived from the macroscopic and microscopic appearance⁸. The pathogenesis of cystic ameloblastomas remains obscure. Some investigators believe that UA arises from preexisting odontogenic cysts, in particular a dentigerous cyst, while others maintain that it arises de novo⁹.

Radiographically, the unilocular: multilocular ratio is 13:3 when the lesion is associated with an impacted tooth. For the “non dentigerous” variant, this ratio changes to 8:7. Further, the

“dentigerous” type occurs on average 8 years earlier than the “non dentigerous” variant. Finally, the mean age for unilocular, impaction-associated UAs is 22 years, whereas the mean age for the multilocular lesion unrelated to an impacted tooth is 33 years¹⁰.

Ackermann et al¹¹.classified unicystic ameloblastoma into three types with prognostic and therapeutic implications such as

Group I: Luminal UA (tumor confined to the luminal surface of the cyst)

- Group II: Intraluminal/plexiform UA (nodular proliferation into the lumen without infiltration of tumor cells into the connective tissue wall)
- Group III: Mural (invasive islands of ameloblastomatous epithelium in the connective tissue wall not involving the entire epithelium)

Another histologic subgrouping by Philipsen and Reichart¹²has also been described as follows:

- Subgroup 1: Luminal
- Subgroup 1.2: Luminal and intraluminal
- Subgroup 1.2.3: Luminal, intraluminal, and intramural
- Subgroup 1.3: Luminal and intramural

Management of ameloblastoma can be done in three ways (1) conservative which includes enucleation and curettage, as well as the use of adjuvant therapies such as Carnoy’s solution and cryotherapy, (2) marsupialization, and (3) radical surgery, which includes marginal or block resection (1–1.5 cm margins result in the highest chance of local control) and immediate bone reconstruction. Iliac crest grafts or microvascular fibular flaps may be required for facial reconstruction procedures¹³. Radiotherapy should be considered in patients with positive margins in whom re-resection is not recommended and for those with incompletely resectable tumours. In our case, we performed local excision with segmental resection of the mandible with a safety margin of 1 cm to avoid recurrence and flap repair for reconstruction¹⁴.

For conventional ameloblastomas, recurrence rates of 50 to 90% have been observed following curettage and up to 15% after marginal or block resection. For this reason, close

and prolonged follow-up examinations should be performed. Conventional radiography and clinical examination may fail to detect recurrences¹⁵. CT is the most sensitive imaging technique for detecting ameloblastoma, and is to be recommended whenever possible.

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